

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

SU 1401 SEEMS TO BE AN ACCUMULATION LAYER CUT BY SU1229. IT CONTAINS LITTLE POTTERY AND ANIMAL BONE AND COVERS WHAT APPEARS TO BE 2 DIFFERENT FLOOR PHASES: IN THE NORTH THE CONTINUATION OF TUFO FLOOR 1173 AND IN THE SOUTHERN HALF AN OLDER LOWER PHASE THAT IS ASSOCIATED WITH THE ENTRY (THRESHOLD SU 1314) LEVEL. VERY SOUTHERN END AND EDGE NEXT TO WALL 1058 SEEMS TO SLOPE DOWNWARD AND LOWER FLOOR SEEMS TRUNCATED POSSIBLY BY A FOUNDATION CUT FOR THE WALL BUT FURTHER EXCAVATION IS NEEDED.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

CHARCOAL

Size: VERY SMALL →

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

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